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THE ROLE OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL TOURISM IN THE FORMATION OF HISTORICAL CITIES OF THE FERGHANA REGION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role, problems and proposals for the development of archeological tourism in the formation and development of historical cities in Fergana region.*

Keywords: *Monument, archeological, territories, resource, stratum.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются роли, проблемы и предложения по развитию археологического туризма в формировании и развитии исторических городов Ферганской области.*

Ключевые слова: *Памятник, археологический, территории, ресурсы, пласт.*

Annotatsiya. *Bu maqolada Farg'ona viloyatida tarixiy Shaharlarnig hsakllanishi va rivojlanish taraqqiyotida arxeologik turizmni rivojlantirish o'rni, muammo va takliflari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yodgorlik, arxeologik, xududlar, resuros, qatlam.*

Introduction. Currently, views on archaeological tourism in different countries have formed differently. Some regions, for various reasons, are losing their unique archaeological sites, and some countries have already managed to turn these regions into tourist centers through museumization. This, in turn, is associated with the political stability of states and, in turn, with high economic potential.

When analyzing the monuments found in the Fergana region, it was found that 30% of them were completely destroyed in the 1980s, 20% were severely damaged, 5% were partially damaged. Currently, more than 30% of archaeological sites are used as cemeteries. This situation leads to the complete disappearance of the cultural layers of the upper part of the monuments. The bulk of the monuments (84%) are settlements, cities, ancient graves and outbuildings of various types.

It is also advisable to organize exhibitions of special photographs and works of fine art at each archaeological site that reflect the nature of the archaeological site and the area where it is located. It is necessary to organize various international and regional conferences, symposiums and festivals in order to ensure regular visits of foreign tourists to the Fergana region in order to carry out certain practical and research work.

Today it is necessary to pay special attention to the implementation of foreign investments and grant programs in order to study existing archaeological sites. This, in turn, will be of great importance in establishing systematic activities for the restoration and preservation of archaeological monuments.

In 2013, employees of the Institute of Archeology of the Federal Republic of Uzbekistan will conduct archaeological observation work with the aim of creating an archaeological map of the Fergana region. During the research, 177 archaeological sites were recorded as a result of scientific work, archival data and direct observation of regional archaeological sites. Of these, 153 monuments were directly recorded on N. Gorbunova's 1979 map, and more than 20 monuments were identified during archaeological research carried out in subsequent years.

In particular, the burial places of Koktash, Galasak, the Moy Mubarak monuments, the Fergana Museum of History and Local Lore G. Ivanov, Mashadtepa, Surkhtepa, Kyzlarmozor, Tepakorgan were also studied by researchers from the Institute of Archeology of the Russian Federation. recorded. The Tepakorgan monument, located in the city of Kokan, was built in 2008 by architect A.A. He was identified by Kokan's detachment under the leadership of Anarbaev. In 2011, large-scale archaeological excavations were carried out here. As a result, it became known that an urban settlement formed here in the first century BC and the beginning of our era, which operated until the Arab invasion.

At the same time, as a result of archaeological observation work in 2013, a number of new monuments were identified, including the rock art monuments of Vodila (Fergana region), Mataibuva, Shortepa (Koshtepa region). In particular, the recently discovered sites of Mataibuva and Shortepa have a diameter of 15-20 m and a height of 2-2.5 m.

Archaeological sites, in turn, are considered a bridge connecting the past with the present. At the same time, we must not forget that it is a silent witness to the ancient past. Today, the role of archaeological sites in the development of tourism in villages and small towns is incomparable. By restoring and reconstructing archaeological sites in these areas, there will be an opportunity to enhance the pride and pride of the local population.

Conclusion. The development of tourism in our country coincides with the period of renewal of society and is aimed at further improving its quality, taking into account

the process of gradual changes occurring. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, there are enough tourist and resource opportunities for the development of tourism that meet the requirements of the present time.

As a result of studying the possibilities for the effective use of tourism resources, ways to improve the efficiency of their use, factors influencing them and their identification, as well as assessing the possibilities for using tourism resources, theoretical and practical aspects of increasing economic efficiency are studied. Effectiveness, the following conclusions were drawn and recommendations were developed:

1. The high potential of tourism resources of the Fergana region, that is, the presence of cultural and historical monuments, rich historical heritage, religious, environmental, scientific and unique traditions and other characteristics, allow the development of tourism based on the requirements of the time. This requires food. Effective use of the potential of tourism resources is the reason for the active economic process, and its possibilities have not yet been sufficiently studied by scientists of our republic.

Accordingly, it is necessary to conduct research work on this topic in our republic, to develop appropriate proposals and recommendations on many of its theoretical and practical issues.

2. Tourism resources are of great socio-economic importance, especially their effective use has a positive impact on the lives of the local population. These positive features were based on:

- wounds of places of irritation;
- increasing income, improving the standard of living of the local population;
- acceleration of social and cultural processes;
- creation of local cultural centers, development of folk art, traditions, customs;
- increasing demand for agricultural products and locally produced goods;
- restoration and protection of local cultural monuments;
- expansion of natural complexes;
- increasing the attractiveness of the region;
- revitalization of local cultural life, etc.

REFERENCES:

1. Zohidovna, M. N. (2021). The Basic Principles of the use of Building Materials in the Repair of Decorations of Architectural Monuments of Uzbekistan. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 2(12), 19-23.
2. Adabiyotga 5. Muminova, N. Z., Toshmatov, U. T., & Norimova, S. A. (2020). In Uzbekistan roof landscaping-the need for environmental health, convenience, beauty. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 213-215.
3. Salimov, A., Xotamov, A., Juraboyev, A., & Muminova, N. (2023). Architectural planning solutions of recreational facilities in mountainous areas. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 452, p. 06028). EDP Sciences.
4. Н.З. Муминова. (2022). История И Карта Древнего Парканское (Даванское) Государства Ферганское Долины. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12, 129–132. Retrieved from <https://periodica.org/index.php/journal/article/view/279>
5. Juraboev, A. (2023). URBAN PLANNING AND ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF THE NATURAL LANDSCAPE ENVIRONMENT OF UZBEKISTAN. *Journal of Construction and Engineering Technology*, 1(2), 1–4.
6. Jo‘Raboyev, A. T. O. G. (2022). PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZING RECREATION SPACES IN THE MOUNTAIN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 248-253.
7. Tolibjon o‘g, J. R. A. (2023). PRINCIPLES OF CREATING RECREATIONAL FACILITIES IN MOUNTAINOUS AREAS. *Conferencea*, 52-58.
8. Tolibjon o‘g, J. R. A. (2023, November). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CREATING RECREATIONAL FACILITIES IN THE MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS OF FERGANA REGION. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 44-48).
9. Salimov Arifdjan Muslimovich, & Kurganov Uktamjon, Kurganova Zulayho. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF ISLAMIC PHILOSOPHY TO RESIDENCES OF THE HISTORICAL CITY OF MARGILAN. *Academia Science Repository*, 4(04), 332–336.
10. Salimov Arifdjan Muslimovich, & Kurganov Uktamjon, Kurganova Zulayho. (2023). VOLUME-SPATIAL AND COMPOSITION SOLUTIONS OF MARGILAN TRADITIONAL HOUSES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 193–196.
11. Muminova, N. . Z. (2024). THE FORMATION OF THE CITY OF MARGILAN (OLD MARGILAN) IN THE HISTORY OF ARCHITECTURE. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 676–680. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/6178>
12. Muminova, N. . Z. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL FERGANA CITY CENTERS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 690–694. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/6180>